

Cloud Services for Autonomous Interaction With Social Robots and Artificial Agents

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Abstract—This work presents the design and the implementation of CAIR: a cloud system for knowledge-based interaction devised for Social Robots and other conversational agents. The system is structured in a way that it can be easily expanded by adding new services that improve the capabilities of the clients connected to the Cloud. Another key feature of the system is that it has been designed to make the development of its clients straightforward: in this way, multiple devices (e.g., robots, computers, smartphones, etc.) can be easily endowed with the capability of autonomously interacting with the user, understanding when to perform specific actions, and exploiting all the information provided by services on the Cloud.

Index Terms—Cloud Robotics, REST API, Client-Server Architecture, Socially Assistive Robots, Human-Robot Interaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

CARESSSES¹ is an international, multidisciplinary project whose goal is to design the first robots that can assist older people and adapt to the culture of the individual they are taking care of [1]. The robots can help the users in many ways including reminding them to take their medication, encouraging them to keep active, helping them keep in touch with family and friends. Each action is performed with attention to the older person's customs, cultural practices and individual preferences. In CARESSSES, the ability of the companion robot to naturally converse with the user has been achieved by creating a framework for cultural knowledge representation that relies on an Ontology [2]. A major limitation of the CARESSSES system is that only one device at a time can connect to the server and exploit all the capabilities provided by the system. Moreover, its server stores the information related to a single client, and it manages all the connections, even from different devices, as coming from the same user. This kind of implementation also prevents the system to allow for an expansion of the knowledge base from multiple users.

Recently, it has become more and more common to exploit cloud technologies to improve the efficiency of many devices and systems. In the robotics field, this practice is defined as *cloud robotics*, i.e. the use of remote computing resources to enable greater memory, computational power, collective learning and inter-connectivity for robotics applications [3].

This paper describes the cloud system that has been designed based on the underlying principles of the CARESSSES

system, but completely modifying its architecture to offer a set of web services for multiple robots and devices.

The CAIR system has been developed by taking advantage of the rich knowledge base and the dialogue mechanism developed during the CARESSSES project, intending to create a system much easier to use and able to manage contemporary connections from multiple users. The system is based on the use of REST APIs [4] that provide many advantages such as scalability, flexibility, portability and independence (see Section II). CAIR web services allow the connected clients to manage a rich conversation with the users and to receive Plans to be executed, if possible, on the client device. Moreover, such architecture allows to effectively exploit the already implemented mechanism for knowledge expansion [5], which will be integrated into the following versions of the system.

The system for knowledge-based autonomous interaction described in this work can be easily used by most devices with Internet connectivity, able to acquire an input through a keyboard or a microphone, and provide an output through a screen or a speaker (e.g., robots, computers, smartphones, smartwatches, etc.).

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The architecture of the system is composed of a server that manages an Ontology containing all the concepts and sentences that can be used during an interaction. The server is able to analyze the user sentence to recognize both commands to execute actions and the intention of talking about a specific topic. On the other side, the client acquires the user's sentence, sends it to the server, parses the response, executes the received Plan and/or replies with the sentence reply.

A. Server

The server is composed of a set of services implemented as REST APIs using Python. In particular, the Flask-RESTful² framework has been used. The architecture of the server has been designed in a way that makes it easy to add new services if necessary.

The first thing that the server does once the Dialogue Manager service is started, is to retrieve all the fundamental information for the dialogue from the Ontology, then it waits for a PUT or a GET request.

¹www.caressesrobot.org

²<https://flask-restful.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

1) *PUT request*: The PUT request does not require any parameter and it returns to the client its initial state. The latter includes the current topic of conversation, the type of sentence chosen by the system (for instance a yes/no question, open question, assertion, etc.), the type of the following sentences that the system should use for that topic, and other information. Along with the client state, the PUT request also returns the first sentence to start the conversation.

2) *GET request*: The GET request requires as parameters the user’s sentence and the client state. The sentence is sent to the Intent matching service (another REST API on the server) with the purpose of finding a match between the user’s sentence and a specific Intent. An Intent is defined by (i) a set of trigger sentences (built using regexes), (ii) one or more intent-specific answers (if any), (iii) a KBPlan (if any), (iv) and a Plan (if any).

A KBPlan, where KB stands for Knowledge Base, is a sequence of actions meant to affect the knowledge base and/or the flow of the dialogue. For instance, if the user says “*I love music*”, this sentence will match one of the trigger sentences of the Intent that recognizes the user’s appreciation for something and extracts the loved thing as a parameter. The KBPlan of this Intent is composed of two actions: the first one is meant to increase the probability that the user wants to talk about the extracted parameter, while the second one brings the information that the system should jump to that conversation topic (if present in the Ontology).

A Plan is a sequence of actions that should be executed on the client as it does not affect the knowledge base nor the flow of the dialogue. For instance, if the user says “*Play the song Yesterday*”, this sentence will match one of the trigger sentences of the Intent that recognizes the user intention to some music. The Plan of this Intent is composed of a single action carrying the information that the client should play the song having the title contained in the parameter field (see Section II-B). Note that, instead of having predefined KBPlans and Plans, the Intent matching service could call a planning service that creates Plans based on the matched Intent.

If a match with an Intent is found, a response containing the Intent reply, the KBPlan, and the Plan is returned to the Dialogue Manager service. The KBPlan is managed by the Dialogue Manager, as it directly affects the continuation of the dialogue, while the Intent reply and the Plan are not used by this service. Once the main service has chosen the most appropriate answer for the user based on the information contained in the client state, the previous user’s sentence, and, eventually, the KBPlan, it returns a response to the client. Such a response contains the updated client state, the Intent reply, the Plan, and the reply of the system (i.e., the actual continuation of the dialogue).

B. Client

As already mentioned in Section I, a client for CAIR can be easily developed for most devices with Internet connectivity such as robots, computers, smartphones, smartwatches, etc. The first thing that the client should do is to perform a PUT

Fig. 1. CAIR system architecture

request to the server, in particular to the Dialogue Manager service, to obtain the initial client state and the first sentence of the conversation. The client state should be stored locally and retrieved before all the following requests. Afterwards, the client should acquire the user input, send it to the server along with the client state with a GET request, retrieve and manage the response. This last operation expects the system to communicate the Intent reply to the user, perform the actions contained in the plan field of the response, and eventually continue the dialogue by communicating the sentence reply. If the client is not able to execute the actions it can ignore them and consider only the sentence reply.

Figure 1 depicts the architecture of the system and summarizes all the parameters involved.

An example of a simple client for PC can be found in this GitHub repository³. The repository contains also a PDF guide with a detailed explanation of the code and of all Plans that the server can return to the client based on the Intent that has been matched. Another documented example of a full client for the SoftBank Robotics robots Pepper and Nao, that manages all the Plans returned by the server, can be found here⁴. A video showing some extracts of the interaction is available on YouTube⁵.

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³https://github.com/lucregrassi/CAIRclient_instructions.git

⁴<https://github.com/lucregrassi/CAIRclient/tree/develop>

⁵<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UdbYGytd07w>